

A Bibliometric Analysis of Digital Technologies Used in Health Promotion Interventions

Michael Daka¹, Christopher Dick-Sagoe², Mogopodi Hazel Lekorwe³, and David Mandiyanike⁴
Department of Political and Administrative Studies, University of Botswana, Gaborone, Botswana, Southern Africa^{1,2,3}
Department of Development Studies, University of South Africa, South Africa⁴

Over the past two decades, digital technologies have transformed health promotion delivery from the traditional face-to-face to internet-based platforms. This study explored the research trends, hotspots and emerging themes in the digital health promotion research. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) was used to collect data from the Scopus database using digital technologies and health promotion keywords. Bibliometric analysis was used to map research trends and hotspots while thematic analysis was used to identify the main themes. The results show that 1,366 papers were retrieved and 48 of them were included in the study for themes identification. The annual publications increased over time, with a tremendous increase in the past five years due to the growth of interests by researchers in digital technologies, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. The leading journal and country on digital health promotion research are the Journal of Medical Internet Research and the United States of America, respectively. Digital technologies available for health promotion are mobile apps, wearable devices, artificial intelligence, social media and websites. These have been used to connect health professionals with individuals and empower them with the capacity to make decisions regarding their health. However, a digital divide exists among internet users including health professionals. The study concludes that the use of digital technologies has a great potential to promote health and recommends that governments and health institutions promote digital literacy among internet users.

Keywords: Digital technologies, health promotion, bibliometric analysis and systematic review

Digital technologies and health promotion collaborate to improve the health outcomes of the people. Worldwide, the use of digital technologies is happening at an unprecedented scale (WHO, 2021). It has changed the landscape in which health education is made available and accessible in the past two decades (Koh et al., 2021). Individuals are now able to access health education and connect with health promotion professionals. Digital technologies have the potential to support the development of online communities and support groups. They enhance social interactions and peer support that are crucial in enabling behaviour change (Bakken et al., 2019).

In the recent past, digital technologies have seen tremendous growth. An increasing number of government and health institutions are using digital technologies to promote health. Digital technologies such as mobile apps and social media platforms are

available for people in communities and health promotion professionals to use in disease prevention and promotion of healthy living. During the COVID-19 pandemic, governments and health institutions used digital technologies to conduct awareness campaigns and provide health education on the public health management guidelines (Tahmasbi et al., 2025). Therefore, it is crucial to understand the role of digital technologies in health promotion and in particular, to answer the following research questions: 1) How has the digital technology literature in health promotion progressed over time? 2) What are the main journals, countries, and institutions in this field? 3) What are the main keywords associated with digital technologies in health promotion research? 4) What are the various themes that the literature on digital technologies and health promotion revolves around?

Author Note

¹Michael Daka, Department of Political and Administrative Studies University of Botswana, Gaborone, Botswana, Southern Africa
E-mail: 202304991ub.ac.bw, michael.daka@cbu.ac.zm

²Christopher Dick-Sagoe, Department of Development Studies University of South Africa, South Africa

³Mogopodi Hazel Lekorwe, Department of Political and Administrative Studies, University of Botswana, Gaborone Botswana, Southern, Africa

⁴David Mandiyanike, Department of Political and Administrative Studies, University of Botswana, Gaborone, Botswana, Southern Africa

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Michael Daka, Department of Political and Administrative Studies University of Botswana, Gaborone, Botswana, Southern Africa
E-mail: 202304991ub.ac.bw, michael.daka@cbu.ac.zm

Method

The study adopted a systematic review and used the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) framework to screen the results and explain the selection and rejection of papers to review digital technologies in health promotion as shown in Figure 1. The PRISMA framework is important in systematic literature review because it assist to improve the writing of a review paper.

Data Source

We systematically searched Scopus database in June 2025 using 2 keywords namely; digital technologies AND health promotion. This database was chosen because it provides a wider selection of high impact journal articles due to huge volume of publications when compared to other data bases (Sikandar, Vaicondam, Khan, Qureshi, & Ullah, 2021).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The study included peer-reviewed papers: (1) published from 1980 - 2024 for descriptive analysis; (2) journal articles published in open access in fields such as medicine, computer studies, social sciences, health professional and nursing from 2020-2024, in open access and in English. This was done to narrow the focus of the study and ensure that only high impact papers were included for the review.

The study excluded: (1) papers published before 2020 for systematic review, (2) papers neither published in open access nor in fields such as medicines, computer studies, social sciences, health professional and nursing and published in other languages other than English from 2020 -2024. Books, reviews and conference papers were excluded to ensure only the quality of papers was maintained by reviewing peer-reviewed papers only. This was done to ensure that relevant and impactful papers were used for the review.

Data Extraction and Synthesis

Two researchers independently searched papers based on the study inclusion and exclusion criteria. They screened titles and abstracts and made decisions on the papers to include. In case of disagreement, the researchers consulted the third researcher on the way forward. Descriptive analysis has been used to answer the first and second research questions. For the third research question, we conducted a co-occurrence of keywords analysis to identify the main research areas related to digital technologies in health promotion research. To answer the fourth research question, we manually analyzed 48 records to identify themes in the literature that have received attention in the past five years in the field.

Risk of Bias

The study did not use any methodological quality evaluation tool. This is because the study aimed to map research trends and themes in digital health promotion, not to assess methodological rigor or intervention effectiveness. Several sources of bias may affect the results. Exclusive use of the Scopus database could have excluded relevant studies from other sources, resulting in database selection bias (Falagas, Pitsouni, Malietzis, & Pappas, 2008). Limiting the review to open-access, English-language journal articles published between 2020 and 2024 in selected subject areas may have introduced language and disciplinary bias. Dependence on published literature may reflect publication bias, as studies with positive findings are more likely to appear in the literature (Song et al., 2010). Citation-based indicators may prioritize research visibility over quality (Aksnes, Langfeldt, & Wouters, 2019). Therefore, the findings reflect the visible and indexed scholarly landscape in Scopus, not a comprehensive account of global research.

Ethical Approval and Informed Consent Statement

Data for systematic review and descriptive analysis were searched and downloaded from the Scopus database. These are publicly available data. The extraction of this data did not involve interaction with human beings or animals. Thus, there were no ethical issues concerning the use of the extracted data, and hence, no approval from an ethics committee was needed.

Results

Search Results

We retrieved 1,366 publications, with the oldest dating back to 1980,

for descriptive analysis. In addition, the study identified 988 potentially relevant papers published from 2020-2024 through the screening. These papers were also screened for their eligibility. We set a limit of only open-access journal articles, articles published in English, and published in medicine, health promotions, social sciences and computer studies. This resulted in 408 papers. Out of these papers, 48 papers out of 408 were selected based on their relevance to the research questions.

Figure 1

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews with Meta-analysis (PRISMA) Framework

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis was used to answer the first and second research question.

Publication Outputs

The annual publications on digital technologies in health promotion increased since 1980 with significant increase in the past 5 years as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2

Publications Per Year

Most Productive Journals

The number of publications on digital technologies in health promotion was distributed across 149 journals. Figure 3 shows the top ten (10) journals that published articles on digital technologies in health promotion. The Journal of Medical Internet published the highest number of papers (73), followed by the International Journal of Environment Research and Public Health (46), and then Frontiers in Public Health (22).

Figure 3*Most Productive Journals**Distributions of Publications in Countries*

Figure 4 shows the 10 top countries with the highest number of publications in research on digital technologies in health promotion. The top 4 countries are the United States (394), the United Kingdom (186), Australia (123) and China (109).

Figure 4*Countries with Most Publications**Top Institutions*

Figure 5 shows the top 11 institutions actively involved in digital technologies in health promotion. The leading institution is the Harvard Medical School. This is followed by the University College London, the University of Washington and the Universität Bremen.

Figure 5*Institutions Actively Involved in Digital Health Promotion Research Bibliometric Analysis*

We carried out a bibliometric analysis and conducted a co-occurrence of key words to answer the third research question.

Co-occurrence of Key Words Analysis

The VOS viewer software was used to identify the most popular keywords used in digital health literature. 3531 keywords were shown in the software. The minimum number of occurrences of a keyword was set to 22 to reduce the number of keywords to manageable limits. This resulted in 25 keywords, as shown in Figure 6. The findings of this research show that the most used keywords in

digital technologies are digital health, mhealth, telehealth, eHealth, COVID-19, digital technology, technology, and health literacy. The popular digital technologies used in health promotion are artificial intelligence, mobile apps, and social media. The emerging topics in the digital health literature, as shown in Figure 6, are digital technologies, public health, health literacy, COVID, and mobile phones, telemedicine and promotion. Digital health and mHealth are the most popular keywords. The software also shows that mental health, health, healthcare, health literacy, physical activity, COVID-19 and mobile phone are the most emerging topics in digital health literature.

Figure 6*Co-occurrence of Author Keywords**Emerging Themes on Digital Technologies in Health Promotion*

Through thematic analysis of the 48 articles on the literature published in the period 2020-2024, the following themes have been identified: digital technologies in health promotion; digital divide; application of digital health promotion and digital health promotion and COVID-19.

Digital Technologies in Health Promotion

Digital technologies have become increasingly important in helping people access and understand public health information (Lee & Tak, 2022). They have emerged as a key component of promoting healthy behaviors (Aung et al., 2022). Technologies such as mobile apps, wearable, artificial intelligence and online platforms (websites & social media) have been widely used in health promotion activities (Peng et al., 2020; Ramsey et al., 2020; Glasgow et al., 2021). Health promotion professionals can leverage these technologies with appropriate user-informed adaptations based on individual characteristics, preferences or needs (Slater et al., 2020) and engage internet users in their usage (Götzl et al., 2022). For example, an AI Chatbot (SnehAI) developed by the Population Foundation of India, deliberately designed for social and behavioral changes in India engaged its users through messages to talk and learn about sensitive health issues (Wang et al., 2022).

Digital technologies can help to ensure that health education is made available and accessible even by hard-to-reach individuals (Glasgow et al., 2021; Slater et al., 2020). It can make people not only seek, understand and evaluate health information but also apply and share acquired knowledge (Slater et al., 2020). These technologies provide an easy but cost-effective way to reach out to people on public health matters compared to the traditional face-to-face approach (Koh et al., 2021). They can also provide self-support

care to individuals through timely reminders to take medication, do physical exercises, and ultimately staying health, thereby leading to changes in the behaviour of individuals (Aung et al., 2022; Ramsey et al., 2020; Glasgow et al., 2021).

Digital Divide

The systematic review shows a significant digital divide with differences in access to and utilization of digital technologies in health promotion. The factors that contribute to this divide are socioeconomic status, age, geographical location, and digital literacy. Individuals who are older adults, less educated, reside in rural areas and belong to ethnic minorities do not have access to the internet (Fareed et al., 2021; Götzl et al., 2021) while the young and higher household income earners have access to the internet (De Santis, Jahnel, Sina, Wienert, & Zeeb, 2021). Young people use mobile health apps regularly to make health decisions and have a more positive attitude about the application of AI in health promotion/prevention than older adults (Götzl et al., 2021). This affects the health and quality of life for older adults (Jung, Son, & Choi, 2022).

The systematic review also highlights low digital health literacy among many internet users. It shows that there is low comprehension of digital health literacy by a majority of internet users including health promotion professionals (Maeda et al., 2020). According to a study, less than half of internet users in Germany were confident in using digital information for health decisions despite the perceived eHealth literacy being high (De Santis et al., 2021). Low digital literacy levels have made the majority of internet users have a negative view about the usage of AI in mobile health application in promoting health (Götzl et al., 2022).

Application of Digital Health Promotion

Digital health promotion is the application of information and communication technologies in health promotion. The adoption of digital technologies in health promotion has led to a dramatic shift from the traditional face-to-face communication of public health information to online dissemination of public health information (De Santis et al., 2021). Digital technologies have been widely used in the provision of health education (Peng et al., 2020), to individuals with Cancer (Fareed et al., 2021), Asthma (Maeda et al., 2020), and mental health (Götzl et al., 2022). They have also been used to provide health education to improve fertility knowledge and interventions to optimize preconception behaviour (Maeda et al., 2020) and on the type of physical activities meant to improve the well-being of individuals (Aung et al., 2022; Cheng, Elsworth, & Osborne, 2021). They are also used in medication management. They provide timely reminders on the need to take medication (Ramsey et al., 2020; Glasgow et al., 2021). Despite its significance, digital health promotion is faced with challenges of ensuring privacy control, appropriate usage of data by individuals beyond the original intention, the right of choice and ensuring widespread accessibility of public health information (Koh et al., 2021).

Digital Health Promotion and the COVID-19 Pandemic

The use of digital technologies increased rapidly during the COVID-19 pandemic particularly for disease prevention and health education (Gómez-Ramírez et al., 2021). This made health promotion professionals, governments and health institutions conduct awareness campaigns meant to disseminate COVID-19

information to individuals (Ramsey et al., 2020). In particular, social media platforms such as Twitter and Facebook are increasingly become the effective means to communicate COVID-19 messages to the citizens. For example, in Colleges and Universities, digital psycho-education was adopted as a means to promote healthy living and the prevention of the spread of COVID-19 among students. The information provided included healthy lifestyles, common emotional reactions to COVID-19, coping strategies, and warning signs (Zapata-Ospina et al., 2021). The messages or information accessed acted as a source of comfort for those who had developed mental distress due to COVID-19 (Cosgrove, Karter, Morrill, & McGinley, 2020).

Discussion

In this paper, we explored literature on digital technologies in health promotion. The review shows that the number of annual publications of scientific papers in this field has been increasing since 1980 with particularly notable increase in the past 5 years. This increase is partially attributed to the significant growth of interests by researchers in the field of digital health promotion during the COVID-19 pandemic. The highest number of these publications were in the Journal of Medicine Internet Research with the United States (394/1366) contributing most of the papers. Further, the United States has two institutions actively involved in digital health promotion in the top 4, namely the Harvard Medical School and the University of Washington. This finding suggests that the United States is the global leader in digital health promotion research. The review also shows that China is the only developing country in the top 4 leading countries with 109 publications. This finding demonstrates a growing research capacity by developing countries in contributing to digital health research and innovation.

The systematic review also shows that digital technologies such as mobile apps, wearable, Artificial Intelligence and online platforms such as websites and social media have been extensively used to promote health behaviour. During the COVID-19 pandemic, these technologies have been used to promote healthy behaviour and prevent the spread of COVID-19 by governments and other health institutions. Despite the significance of these technologies, the review show that there is low comprehension of digital health literacy by a majority of internet users including health promotion professionals¹⁵. This finding suggests a need for improved digital literacy among internet users especially health promotion professionals. The digital literacy for both health promotion professionals and individuals are crucial for successful online health promotion.

Our findings align with previous research indicating a growing interest of researchers on digital health promotion research. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated this interests and led to the highest number of publications on digital health promotion research in the past 5 years. Most of these publications were published by the Journal of Medicine Internet Research. This journal is the most impactful journal in the broader field of digital health.²⁵ Contrary to previous findings indicating European countries being the global leaders in digital health research, our review shows that countries like China have emerged to be in the top 4 leading countries globally. This is attributed to the adoption of digital technologies since the emergency of COVID-19 in China and the growth of interest by researchers on digital health promotion during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In this systematic review, we observed that digital technologies such as mobile applications have been very instrumental in the sharing of public health information to the people and the promotion of health behaviour. The COVID-19 escalated the use of mobile apps in the dissemination of public health management guidelines through websites and social media platforms. Smart phones have been the commonly used platform for eHealth program.²⁶ These phones can be used to adopt healthy behaviors such as adherence to medication, physical exercises, reasonable diet and obesity prevention.²⁷ However, the review shows that many health promotion professionals have low digital literacy. This is one reason why the usage of digital technologies in health is not widespread.²⁵ It is important that health promotion professionals are vested with the usage of information communication technologies for the health sector to be impactful in promoting health behaviour.

Limitations

Several limitations affect this study. Reliance on the Scopus database may have restricted the range of retrieved publications, potentially omitting studies indexed in sources such as Web of Science or PubMed. Including only open-access, English-language journal articles published between 2020 and 2024 may have limited the diversity of perceptions, especially from non-English-speaking regions. Additionally, bibliometric indicators such as citation counts measure research visibility rather than methodological rigor or practical impact. Future research should expand database coverage, include non-English publications, and use mixed bibliometric approaches such as altmetric analysis to capture broader patterns of knowledge dissemination and influence in digital health promotion field.

Conclusion

Through a systematic review and bibliometric analysis of data extracted from the Scopus database on digital technologies in health promotion, the study has shown that the number of published papers has increased in the last past five years. One of the possible reason for the increase is the adoption of digital technologies during the COVID-19 pandemic by governments and health institutions whereby health promotion activities were digitalized. The study findings reveal that the USA, UK, Australia and China are the global leaders in digital health promotion research. Further, the Journal of Medical Internet Research is the top journal with most of publications in the digital health promotion research.

The findings also show that digital technology has not only made it possible for public health information to be available and accessed easily but has also made it possible for health professions to connect with individuals on health matters. However, there exists challenges in accessing and utilization of digital technologies by many internet users including health promotion professionals. Therefore, it is important to build capacity to the health promotion professionals with digital literacy so as to raise the ability for them to effectively engage internet users. The findings of this study can help governments, health institutions and individuals to understand the importance of digital health promotion that can make a formidable force to leverage future public health emergencies. Our study recommend that governments and health institutions promote digital literacy and collaborate on health promotion activities.

So What?

What is Already known on the Topic?

Digital technologies play critical roles in providing health education. Technologies such as social media, smartphones apps, wearable and websites are available for individuals to enhance their well-being. These technologies have potential to promote health.

What does this Add?

The adoption of digital technologies such as mobile apps, artificial intelligence, and social media in health promotion have increased tremendously in the past 5 years' due growth of interest by researchers, governments and other health institutions, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the usage of digital technologies in health promotion is not wide spread due to low digital health literacy by many internet users including health professionals.

What are the Implications for Health Promotion Practitioners or Research?

Institutions of higher learning providing health courses should consider introducing mandatory information communication technology courses for health students. In addition, there is need for health institutions and governments to invest in digital technologies and capacity building for health promotion professionals on information communication technologies.

Author Contributions

MD conceptualized and designed the work, collected, extracted and analysed the data, and drafted the paper. CD-S significantly contributed to collection and extraction of data and revised the paper critically. DM and LHM made significant contribution to the design of the paper and edited the revised paper.

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